

A Kinetic Study of the Solvent Effect of Aquo-DMSO Solvent Systems on an Ion-Dipolar Reaction

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ABSTRACT

Broadly speaking, the acid and alkali catalysed hydrolysis of halides, amides and esters are considered to be ion-dipolar reactions. Hence under this planning the kinetics of the solvent effect of aquo-DMSO media on the catalysed hydrolysis of ester Methyl caprylate was studied separately different reaction media consisting of different concentration of DMSO ranging from 20 to 80% (v/v).

It has been observed that ΔH^* and ΔS^* of the reaction were found to increase simultaneously with increase in ΔG^* values and from this, it has been inferred that the reaction is enthalpy dominating and entropy depleting.

From enhancement in E_c values with increase in DMSO content of the reaction media and from depletion in E_D values with increase in D values of the aquo-DMSO media, it has been inferred that the initial state and the transition states of the reaction are solvated and desolvated respectively.

From the evaluated numerical values of the Iso-kinetic temperature of the reaction which comes to be 325.11, it is concluded there is strong and appreciable interaction between solvent and solute aquo-DMSO.

KEYWORDS: Ion-dipolar reactions, Thermodynamic Activation Parameters, Solvolysis, Solvation Effect, Iso-dielectric, Dimethyl sulphoxide, Barclay-Butler rule, Iso – kinetic temperature, Solvent-Solute Interaction.

INTRODUCTION

Though a large number of

researchers have reported their researches on the solvent effect of various types of reactions, but the study of solvent effect of dipolar aprotic solvent like DMSO, on the usefulness of the solvolytic products of caprylate ester i.e. Caprylic acid as dyes, drugs and synthetic flavour has not been paid a little attention so far.

So, in order to highlight the above noted idea, it was thought essential and useful to investigate about the fact that how the uses of caprylic acid is made more effective for manufacturing quality dyes, drugs and synthetic flavour.

EXPERIMENTAL & CALCULATION

The kinetics of alkali catalysed solvolysis of methyl caprylate was studied by adding different concentration of the aprotic organic co-solvent (DMSO) from 20 to 80% (v/v) in the reaction media at five different temperatures, i. e., 20, 25, 30, 35 and 40°C by using previously reported methods⁵⁻⁶. The specific rate constants were evaluated using second order kinetic equation and have been mentioned in Table-I.

The thermodynamic activation parameters namely free energy of activation (ΔG^*), enthalpy of activation (ΔH^*) and entropy of activation (ΔS^*) of the reaction were determined by using wynne-Jones and Eyring equation⁷ and are synchronised in Table - II.

From the slopes of the Arrhenius plots of $\log k$ versus $1/T$ and that of $\log k_D$ (obtained from interpolation of the plots of $\log k$ against D values of aquo-DMSO solvent system) versus $1/T$ the

values of Iso-composition activation energy (E_c) and Iso-dielectric activation energy (E_D) of the reaction have been evaluated and are recorded respectively in Tables- III and IV.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Solvent effect on the Thermodynamic Activation Parameters of the Reaction:

The evaluated values of the three thermodynamic parameters namely ΔH^* , ΔG^* and ΔS^* are synchronised in Table-II and their variations with mol% of the organic content (DMSO) of the reaction media have shown respectively in figures -1, 2 and 3. On perusal of the data in Table - II, it is found that the values of free energy of activation (ΔG^*) increases with increasing DMSO content of the reaction at all the temperature at which the reaction was studied. At 30°C, values of ΔG^* were recorded increasing from 87.12 kJ/mol to 89.15 kJ/mol with increasing proportion of DMSO from 20 to 80% (v/v). Though the enhancement in ΔG^* values is not very high, however, it is liable to be taken into consideration.

Similar variations in ΔG^* values with increasing mol % of organic solvent of the reaction media have also been reported earlier by Singh & Hafizee *et al.*⁸, Singh & Singh *et al.*⁹. From the plot of ΔG^* against mol % of organic co-solvent (as shown in Fig. -2), it is found that ΔG^* values increases smoothly and non-linearly with gradual addition of DMSO in the reaction media. This finding is indicative of desolvation of reactants as explained and also supported by Elsemony *et al.*¹¹.

So far as the variation in ΔH^* and ΔS^* values are concerned, on going through Table-IV, it is interestingly observed that both of them decrease with gradual increase in the concentration of DMSO in the reaction media at all the temperatures.

On the basis of the relation:-

$$\Delta G^* = \Delta H^* - T\Delta S^*$$

it can be concluded that simultaneous enhancement in ΔG^* values with increase in the values of both the ΔH^* and ΔS^* values is only possible when the extent of increase in ΔH^* is more than that of ΔS^* . The regular enhancement to the greater extent in ΔH^* values in comparison to that of ΔS^* values clearly indicates that the alkali catalysed hydrolysis of methyl caprylate in aquo-DMSO media is enthalpy dominated and entropy inhibited. Moreover, non-linear variation in ΔH^* and ΔS^* values with increasing mol% of DMSO in the reaction media as shown in Fig. -1 and 3 respectively, gives information of the fact that the specific solvation is taking place in aquo-DMSO systems, similar to that as reported by Saville *et al.*¹¹ and it also indicates that the random distribution of the components are not permissible. The similar non-linear variations in ΔS^* and ΔH^* values with increasing mol % of the organic component in the reaction media have also been reported recently by Rajiv Kumar & Singh *et al.*¹², Singh & Sushma¹⁴. The enhancement in both ΔH^* and ΔS^* values also justifies that transition state of the reaction is desolvated and its initial state is solvated in aquo-DMSO reaction media.

Solvent Effect on the Iso-composition Activation Energy (E_c) of the Reaction:

From the slopes of the Arrhenius plots of $\log k$ versus $10^3/T$, the values of Iso-composition activation energy (E_c) of the reaction have been evaluated and recorded in Table-III. From Table-III, it is obvious that iso-composition activation energy values of the reaction go on increasing from 105.84 kJ/mol to 138.68 kJ/mol with increasing concentration of DMSO in the reaction media from 20 to 80% (v/v).

The enhancing trend in the E_{exp}

value may be due to either of the following three causes:

- (i) The initial state is more solvated than the transition state.
- (ii) The transition state is more desolvated than the initial state, and
- (iii) The initial state is solvated and the transition state is desolvated,

Out of these three causes, the third factor seems to be operative in this case as both ΔH^* and ΔS^* values of the reaction as mentioned in Table-II, are found to increase. Such findings have been reported earlier by Singh & Perween *et al.*¹⁹. Similar interpretations have also been found in support of the recently reports Sushma & Singh *et al.*²¹.

Solvent effect on the Iso-dielectric Activation Energy (E_D) of the reaction:

Similar to Iso-composition activation energy (E_C), the values of Iso-dielectric activation energy (E_D) were also calculated from the slopes of the Arrhenius plots of $\log k_D$ versus $10^3/T$.

From the recorded values of the Iso-dielectric activation energy (E_D) of the reaction in Table-IV, it is apparent that with increase in D values of the reaction media from D=60 to D=80, the E_D values go on decreasing from 148.33 kJ/mol to 117.58 kJ/mol respectively.

Since with increase in DMSO content of the reaction media there is decrease in its dielectric (D) values, hence in reverse way it may be inferred that with decrease in D values of the reaction media or with increasing DMSO concentration in it, E_D values also increase similar to increase in E_C values. Thus, E_C and E_D values are complementary to each other.

Similar interpretations for such effect of concentration of the added organic content of the media or of the effect of change in dielectric constants

of the reaction media have also been reported earlier by Singh & Namrata *et al.*²³ and Singh & Singh *et al.*²⁴ and in recent years by Ajeet & Singh *et al.*²⁵ and Hafizee & Singh *et al.*²⁶.

Solvent effect on the Iso-kinetic Temperature of the Reaction and Solvent-solute Interaction in the Aquo-DMSO Reaction Media:

The values of the Iso-kinetic temperature of the reaction were evaluated by using Barclay and Butler relationship¹⁹ which is as follows:

$$(\Delta H^*) = \beta \delta m (\Delta S^*)$$

It is a straight line equation presenting the relationship between enthalpy and entropy of activation. ' β ' is iso-kinetic temperature. From the data available in Table-V, the plots of ΔH^* versus ΔS^* at 30°C were made. From the slope of the obtained straight line, the value of iso-kinetic temperature was found to be 325.11 ≈ 325.0. In the light of Leffler's²⁰ guidelines, from the value of iso-kinetic temperature which is much higher than the standard value 300, it is concluded that in aquo-DMSO media, there is appreciably strong solvent-solute interaction for alkali catalysed solvolysis of methyl caprylate. Similar observations, inferences and interpretations have also been reported earlier by Singh & Navendu *et al.*²⁹ and in recently by Ojha & Singh *et al.*³¹.

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Table - I
Specific Rate Constants Values of Alkali Catalysed Hydrolysis of Methyl caprylate
in Water-DMSO Media
 $k \times 10^2$ in $(\text{dm})^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$

Temp in °C	% of t-DMSO (v/v)						
	20%	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%	80%
20°C	89.08	75.61	60.70	50.13	40.11	32.46	24.67
25°C	182.05	157.98	131.86	112.80	96.52	79.41	63.07
30°C	363.50	333.73	281.13	251.36	218.73	189.71	162.67
35°C	733.50	645.80	600.76	549.79	478.41	434.91	391.02
40°C	1408.64	1318.86	1224.05	1122.28	1052.93	999.08	933.04

Table III
Evaluated Values of Iso-Composition Activation Energy (E_c or E_{exp}) of the
reaction in Water-DMSO Media

% of DMSO (v/v)	20%	30%	40%	50%	60%	70%	80%
E_c values in kJ/mol	105.84	109.38	115.71	118.56	123.99	130.68	138.68

Table - IV
Evaluated Values of Iso-Dielectric Activation Energy (E_D) of the reaction at
different Desired 'D' Values of the Water-DMSO Media

D value	D=60	D=64	D=68	D=72	D=76	D=80
E_D values in kJ/mol	148.33	141.76	134.87	128.80	123.09	117.58

Table II

Consolidated Values of Activation Parameters (ΔH^* , ΔG^* , ΔS^*) of the reaction in Water-DMSO System at different temperatures

ΔH^* , ΔG^* in kJ/Mol and ΔS^* in J/K/ Mol

% of t-butanol	Mol% of t-butanol	ΔH^* in kJ/Mol	20°C		25°C		30°C		35°C		40°C	
			ΔG^*	ΔS^*								
20%	5.94	103.38	87.59	53.87	87.36	53.75	87.12	53.64	86.81	53.64	86.56	53.73
30%	9.77	106.65	87.99	63.68	87.99	63.56	87.34	63.74	87.13	63.37	86.73	63.65
40%	14.40	111.50	88.53	78.39	88.53	78.32	87.78	78.30	87.32	78.51	86.92	78.51
50%	20.17	115.75	88.99	91.33	88.99	91.30	88.05	91.42	87.54	91.58	87.15	91.38
60%	27.49	122.24	89.54	111.61	89.54	111.73	88.40	111.67	87.90	111.49	87.38	111.57
70%	37.09	128.40	90.05	130.88	90.05	130.83	88.76	130.82	88.14	130.71	87.45	130.83
80%	50.27	135.91	90.72	154.21	90.72	154.10	89.15	154.31	88.42	154.18	87.63	154.24

Table V
Variation of ΔH^* , ΔG^* and ΔS^* values of the reaction with mol% of DMSO in water-DMSO media

% of DMSO (v/v)	mol% of DMSO	ΔH^* in kJ/mol	ΔG^* in kJ/mol	ΔS^* in J/K/mol
20%	5.94	103.38	87.12	53.64
30%	9.77	106.65	87.34	63.74
40%	14.40	111.50	87.78	78.30
50%	20.17	115.75	88.05	91.42
60%	27.49	122.24	88.40	111.67
70%	37.09	128.40	88.76	130.82
80%	50.27	135.91	89.15	154.31

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3